

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348327478>

Antibiotics with inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2

Preprint · January 2021

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15306.59845

CITATIONS

0

READS

45

1 author:

Domina Petric

UHC Split

156 PUBLICATIONS 2 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

COVID-19 [View project](#)

The Knot Theory of Mind [View project](#)

Antibiotics with inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Aim is to review the literature and find antibiotics that exert inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2.

Based on the quick literature review promising antibiotic agents that could exert inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2 virus are **rifampicin, doxycycline, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin**. Further clinical research is mandatory to determine the clinical efficacy and dose regimen of these antibiotics for the treatment of symptomatic COVID-19 patients.

RIFAMPICIN

I hypothesized in my previous article (*What is the connection between rifampicin and coronaviruses?*) that rifampicin might be useful treatment in patients hospitalized for (suspected) COVID-19 because of its wide antimicrobial activity, for the treatment of possible bacterial co-infection.

Later on, an *in-silico* study was published by Pathak and coworkers, and authors concluded that **rifampicin appeared as the most promising drug showing a very good binding energy**. Based on

their preliminary insights from *in-silico* studies, they proposed that rifampicin may be repurposed for the treatment of COVID-19¹.

DOXYCYCLINE

Yates and coworkers published a paper in which they presented a series of four high-risk, symptomatic, COVID-19⁺ patients, with known pulmonary diseases, treated with doxycycline with subsequent rapid clinical improvement. Authors concluded that doxycycline is an attractive candidate as a repurposed drug in the treatment of COVID-19 infection, with an established safety profile, strong preclinical rationale, and compelling initial clinical experience. Doxycycline was given in a dose regimen of 100 mg twice daily during 10-14 days².

Gendrot and coworkers published a study in which they tested *in vitro* activity of doxycycline against SARS-CoV-2: doxycycline showed *in vitro* activity on Vero E6 cells infected with a clinically isolated SARS-CoV-2 strain (IHUMI-3) with median effective concentration (EC₅₀) of 4.5 ± 2.9 μM,

compatible with oral uptake and intravenous administrations. Doxycycline interacted both on SARS-CoV-2 entry and in replication after virus entry. Besides its *in vitro* antiviral activity against SARS-CoV-2, doxycycline has anti-inflammatory effects by decreasing the expression of various pro-inflammatory cytokines and could prevent co-infections and superinfections due to broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity³.

Malek and coworkers also recommended doxycycline for COVID-19 treatment as doxycycline has antiviral and anti-inflammatory activities⁴.

CEFUROXIME

Scoping review published by Durojaiye⁵ and coworkers identified significant *in silico* evidence that cefuroxime may be a potential multi-target inhibitor of SARS-CoV-2⁵.

CIPROFLOXACIN, MOXIFLOXACIN

In a study (Marciniec et al, 2020) authors revealed that ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin exert strong capacity for binding to COVID-19 Main Protease (M^{pro}). According to the results obtained from the GOLD docking program,

ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin bind to the protein active site more strongly than the native ligand. When comparing with positive controls, a detailed analysis of the ligand–protein interactions shows that the tested fluoroquinolones exert a greater number of protein interactions than chloroquine and nelfinavir⁶.

CONCLUSION

Based on the quick literature review promising antibiotic agents that could exert inhibitory effect on SARS-CoV-2 virus are **rifampicin, doxycycline, cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin**. Therefore, these antibiotics could be useful in the treatment of symptomatic COVID-19 patients, especially in patients with SARS-CoV-2 pneumonia and in case of bacterial co-infection or superinfection.

Nevertheless, further clinical research is mandatory to determine the clinical efficacy and dose regimen for rifampicin, doxycycline (probably 100 mg twice daily 10-14 days), cefuroxime, ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin.

REFERENCES

1. Pathak Y, Mishra A, Tripathi V. Rifampicin may be repurposed for COVID-19 treatment: Insights from an *in-silico* study. Posted April 14, 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-22546/v1> (cited on January 7, 2021)
2. Yates PA, Newman SA, Oshry LJ, et al. Doxycycline treatment of high-risk COVID-19-positive patients with comorbid pulmonary disease. *Therapeutic Advances in Respiratory Disease*. January 2020. doi:10.1177/1753466620951053
3. Gendrot M, Andreani J, Jardot P, et al. In Vitro Antiviral Activity of Doxycycline against SARS-CoV-2. *Molecules*. 2020;25(21):5064.
4. Malek AE, Granwehr BP, Kontoyiannis DP. Doxycycline as a potential partner of COVID-19 therapies. *IDCases*. 2020;21:e00864.
5. Durojaiye AB, Clarke JD, Stamatiades GA, Wang C. Repurposing cefuroxime for treatment of COVID-19: a scoping review of *in silico* studies [published online ahead of print, 2020 Jun 13]. *J Biomol Struct Dyn*. 2020;1-8.
6. Marciniak K, Beberok A, Pęcak P, et al. Ciprofloxacin and moxifloxacin could interact with SARS-CoV-2 protease: preliminary *in silico* analysis. *Pharmacol Rep*. 2020;72(6):1553-1561.